

Modeling and Control of a Battery Connected Standalone Photovoltaic System

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

ABSTRACT

Nowadays, due to the decrease of conventional energy sources and growing problem of environmental pollution, renewable energy sources are playing a big role in producing electricity. For controlling the standalone PV system, its mathematical modeling is very much necessary. So the modeling of PV system and lead-acid battery by using the corresponding equivalent circuits are discussed. Three independent control loops are used to control the whole standalone system. Those are MPPT control loop for extracting maximum power from PV module, battery control loop for bidirectional power flow between battery and DC-link through bidirectional buck-boost converter and inverter control loop for maintaining stable voltage and current at local load. The stability analysis is performed by using bode plots for both the inverter control loop and buck-boost converter control loop and these control loops are stable for our tuned controller parameters. The system is simulated in MATLAB/SIMULINK and simulation results shown to fulfill the objectives of the standalone PV system. The simulation results prove the effectiveness of the proposed controllers.

Keywords: STANDALONE PV SYSTEM; CONTROL STRATEGY; BATTERY SYSTEM

1. Introduction

Nowadays, most of the energy comes from fossil fuels such as coal, diesel, petrol and gas, which is 80% of our current energy. This energy demand is expected to rise by almost half over the next two decades. Possibly this is causing some fear that our energy resources are starting to run down, which has very serious disturbing consequences on the global quality of life and global economy. This increasing demand of energy has two major impacts like energy crisis and climate change. Also the greenhouse gas production related to energy increases due to rise in energy demand. Globally it is a challenge to reduce the CO₂ emission and offer sustainable, clean and affordable energy.

Solar energy has become a promising, popular and alternative source because of its advantages such as abundance, pollution free, renewability and maintenance free. PV system requires less maintenance as compared to wind, hydroelectric and tidal systems because all these systems require rotating instrument for

energy conversion which is not required for conversion of solar energy to electrical energy. Nowadays, production of PV modules is growing at approximately 25% per year, and the implementation of PV systems on buildings and interconnection to utility networks are rapidly increasing and become major programs of developed countries. Among all available storage devices like batteries, ultra-capacitors, compressed air systems, etc., batteries have the highest importance in PV system as they store energy through the electrochemical process and thus have quick response in both charging and discharging processes. Also battery has high power and energy density which makes it one of the most suitable technologies, used to bridge the power fluctuations generated from PV systems.

The major problem with solar energy is poor conversion efficiency and high installation cost. Worldwide, maximum PV systems are utility connected where large amount of solar power is involved. But due to difficulties in maintaining transmission lines and equipment on isolated islands or remote coastal regions, it is also often difficult to maintain long distance transmission of electrical supplies for utility and domestic purposes. Hence, the use of local generation is often considered as the most convenient and cost effective solution. But due to intermittency nature of solar energy, PV power cannot meet the load demand and that requires a storage device which can solve this problem by its charging and discharging process if it is properly controlled. So the control and operation of a standalone PV system is very important and challenging for the electrical researchers. This challenging problem is the primary motivation of the following research work.

2. Literature review

A PV system uses solar cells to directly convert the solar energy into electrical energy. Simply we can say PV systems are like any other electrical power generating systems, but the equipment used for PV system is different than that used for conventional electro-mechanical generating systems. However, the principles of operation and method of interfacing with other electrical systems remain the same. Mainly PV systems are operated in three modes called standalone mode, grid-connected mode, and hybrid mode. We know nowadays maximum PV systems are utility connected but in remote areas where utility supplies are not available, standalone PV systems are very popular. In standalone PV system solar power is only the source of power and the intermittency issue of solar power can be addressed by introducing storage element to the system. This storage device or battery is very crucial in standalone PV system for maintaining power balance between PV generation and load demand. This type of system creates a hybrid PV/battery system which is capable of providing steady power to the load. In other hand, storage device like battery is not a critical element of grid-connected PV systems, though sometimes it can be used to reduce PV power fluctuations, perform peak shaving and supply emergency power. In A grid-connected PV system, li-ion batteries as backup power supply is used to support the voltage and frequency support through active and reactive power compensation. And the system will able to maintain balance between demand and supply of active and reactive power at any given point of time. Various control strategies of a grid-connected and islanded PV microgrid are studied.

These control techniques are the MPPT control, and voltage-frequency control to provide voltage and frequency support to an islanded microgrid. These control strategies are also useful for control of standalone PV system. The main components of standalone PV systems are PV module, battery and local loads, which need to be well understood for its modeling and control. Among all available storage devices, battery is most suitable for renewable energy application as they have high power and energy density compared to other. And Lead-acid battery is more appropriate for renewable energy application like solar and wind because of its low cost, availability in large size and more mature with recycling at end-of-life. For controlling the PV system its modeling is very much necessary for the researchers and it has to give highest importance. So modeling of PV system is a vital part of this work. Here for system simulation the PV system is modeled using its equivalent circuit and equations. In 1994, J. B. Copetti presents a new normalized model with a battery capacity that shows reasonable agreement with actual data. The study focuses on the lead-acid batteries, because at present these are the most commonly used batteries in PV application owing to their relatively low cost and wide availability.

3. Control strategies

3.1. MPPT control

The maximum power of the PV module changes with external climate conditions. At any operating condition there is only one value of current (I_{mpp}) and one value of voltage (V_{mpp}) that defines the maximum power point (MPP) at which power is maximum (P_{max}), as shown in Figure 1.1. We know the PV current changes with the solar irradiation level, and the PV output voltage changes with the temperature of the PV module. To increase the efficiency of PV array maximum power should be extracted from it. The MPPT control technique allows us to extract the maximum available power from the PV module in any operating condition. So inspired by this recent development, a control strategy for extracting maximum power from a PV array was derived. And this control strategy completely implemented using nonlinear dynamics principles. It is designed in such a way that the MPP becomes a global attractor of the system. Hence, under transient and steady state conditions the system will always converge upon the MPP irrespective of change to the operating conditions. This MPPT technique is implemented by using a boost DC-DC converter, as in standalone PV system it is required to increase the voltage level at the input of the inverter or DC-link capacitor.

Figure 1.1: P-V Curve

Figure 1.2 shows a PV system block diagram with the proposed analog MPPT controller. This system consists of a PV module, a boost converter comprising of an input filter capacitor C, an inductor L, output filter capacitor Cdc, a diode and a controllable switch, regulated by the analog MPPT controller. Here PV module is connected to boost converter along with the analog MPPT controller to regulate the voltage and current of the PV module such that it will operate at MPP by continuously adjusting converter duty cycle. Solar cells show a unique global point at which power is maximum, shown in Figure 1.1. Denoting v and i as the module voltage and current respectively, the array's $v - p$ characteristics exhibits a unique global maximum at the point denoted by (V_{mpp}, P_{max}) , where $v = V_{mpp}$. So the the power p will be maximum at the operating array voltage, $v = V_{mpp}$. Unfortunately, the fundamental problem is that V_{mpp} is an unknown variable.

Figure 1.2: control block diagram

3.2 Battery control

The BSS can provide flexible energy management solutions, which improves the power quality of the PV power generation system. The lead-acid battery is mainly used to provide a steady power to the local load irrespective of source or load power variation. In this standalone PV system, lead-acid battery operates in two modes, in which sometimes it must be charged to store excess energy the excess power from solar source or discharged to supply local load when solar power is not sufficient. The primary objective of the battery converter is to maintain a stable common DC bus voltage. A bidirectional buck-boost DC-DC converter is used to maintain continuous power flow between the DC bus and BSS with a constant DC-link voltage. A constant DC-link voltage is maintained by charging or discharging the lead-acid battery depending on the load change or solar irradiance change. So no matter the battery is charging or discharging, the DC-link voltage should be stable and regulated throughout the operation. For this system the reference DC-link voltage is considered as 200 V, which is determined by the knowledge the boost MPPT control. The bidirectional buck-boost converter is controlled in such a way that the DC bus voltage will remain constant or stable during changes in the solar power or load demand variations.

Figure 1.3: Coordinated control block diagram of the battery

The control strategy for buck-boost converter is shown in Figure 3.3. From this figure it is clear that there are two power MOSFETs in the configuration of converter in which both operates in complimentary way generated signal by the control logic. The pulse driven by PWM signal is used to switch the complimentary way operated MOSFETs for buck or boost operation. The voltage V_{dc} is compared with a reference DC-link voltage V_{dcref} to get the error signal and this error signal is passed through the PI controller to produce I_{batref} . After that the I_{batref} is compared with the sensed battery current to get the error signal and the error obtained is compensated by the PI controller for getting a PWM signal as shown in the Figure 1.3. The PWM signal or control signal is compared with a high frequency triangular signal to get the switching pulses. The switching frequency of this DC-DC converter is taken as 20 kHz. The PI controller parameters for voltage loop are $K_p = 0.08$ and $K_i = 5$ and for current loop are $K_p = 0.1$ and $K_i = 0.05$.

4. Results and discussion

4.1 Nominal condition

First let us assume that the PV power generation is equal to the load demand power, and at that time battery is not supplying or taking any power. In our system at nominal condition PV system produces 2 KW of electrical power. At this condition the standalone PV system is simulated and its steady state output voltage (v_0) and load current (i_0) are shown in Figure 1.4 and Figure 1.5 respectively. This shows the controlling action of the inverter control system. The steady state dc-link voltage is shown in Figure 1.6 along with its reference value. Its proper tracking shows the effectiveness of the battery control by the bidirectional DC-DC converter. The steady state result of V_{mpp} and I_{mpp} are also shown in Figure 4.5 and Figure 4.6 respectively at nominal condition. These two results signify the working and effectiveness of analog MPPT controller. At this time as battery is not storing or giving any power through its charging and discharging process, its SOC curve remains constant throughout shown in Figure 1.7.

Figure 1.4: Steady state output voltage

Figure 1.5: Steady state load current

Figure 1.6: Steady state DC-link voltage

Figure 1.7: Steady state SOC of battery system

4.2 Load variance

As in standalone system solar energy is the only source of energy, battery system is used to mitigate the load demand. Some times when solar energy production is low the battery system can provide the excess energy demanded by the load. When load varies there will be a power mismatch between solar generation and local load, and that power gap can be fulfilled by the use the lead-acid battery system. When load increases the battery have to supply the extra power and when load decreases the battery have to consume this extra power. Here a resistive load is taken for simulation and it is varied like the following $7.5\text{ W} \rightarrow 6\text{ W} \rightarrow 5\text{ W}$, and the simulation results are captured for output voltage, load current, battery's SOC and powers at generation and demand. In other words active power load is varied in the following sequence, $1.6\text{ kW} \rightarrow 2\text{ kW} \rightarrow 2.4\text{ kW}$. For this load variation the steady state output voltage is shown Figure 1.8, which indicates that under load variation the output voltage is remains unchanged and stable. This proves the effectiveness of inverter current control technique which is responsible for maintaining 110 V of constant voltage across the load.

Figure 1.8: Output voltage under load variation

The output load current wave form is shown in Figure 1.9 under the same load variation. From the output current result it is clear about the load variation, as the load current changing after some specified time. But this current waveform has less transient effect which signifies the stability of inverter control loop.

Figure 1.9: Load current under load variation

From the power curves shown in Figure 1.10, it is clear that when PV generation is greater than load power demand, battery starts charging and its SOC increases and when load power demand is more than the PV generation, battery discharges to provide the additional power to the load and its SOC starts decreasing. When the load power demand is same as the PV power generation, battery needs not to take or give any power which keeps its SOC remains constant, shown in Figure 1.11. SOC curve shown in Figure 4.10 reflects the charging and discharging process of BSS according to the load power variation.

Figure 1.10: Output load and battery power under load variation

Figure 1.11: SOC of battery system under load variation

4.3 Solar irradiance

As we know solar power is intermittent in nature, it cannot provide a steady power to the load connected. That means sometimes load power demand is constant, but due to the variation in solar power generation, we need the help of BSS to compensate that extra power. So when PV generation power is not sufficient to mitigate the load demand, BSS needs to provide the extra power through the discharging process and this condition is called underproduction.

Figure 1.12: Output voltage under solar irradiance variation

Figure 1.13: Load current under solar irradiance variation

Figure 1.14: Output load and battery power under solar irradiance variation

Figure 1.12 and Figure 1.13 show the output voltage and load current respectively under solar power variation. The voltage and current wave form are stable and transient free at the load, which shows the proper working of inverter control technique. Solar generated power is varied by varying its irradiance level in the following sequence $800 \text{ W/m}^2 \rightarrow 1000 \text{ W/m}^2 \rightarrow 1200 \text{ W/m}^2$. In Figure 1.14 the power curves are shown, which shows the PV power variation, output power and battery power variation. This power curves gives a clear view of the solar power variation. From this power curves it is clear that when solar power is less than the output power demand, BSS is providing the extra amount of power through discharging process and when solar power is greater than the output power demand, BSS is taking the extra amount of power through charging process. During discharging, battery power is positive and during charging its power is negative, which can be seen from the graph.

5. Conclusion

In this work, three independent control loops are used for the standalone PV system. Those are MPPT control loop for extracting maximum power from PV module, battery control loop for bidirectional power flow between battery and DC bus through buck-boost converter and inverter control loop for maintaining stable voltage and current at local load. The analog MPPT controller is very robust and extracts the maximum power available at the solar panel. A bidirectional buck-boost DC-DC converter is used to maintain continuous power flow between the DC bus and BSS with a constant DC-link voltage. A constant DC-link voltage is maintained by charging or discharging the lead-acid battery depending on the load change or solar irradiance change. In this work a current-controlled single phase VSI with bipolar pulse width modulation is used to maintain the stable voltage and current at local load. The stability analysis is performed by using bode plots for both the inverter control loop and buck-boost converter control loop and these control loops are

stable for our tuned controller parameters. The purpose of using lead-acid battery in standalone PV system is verified by varying load power and solar irradiance level in the simulation. The simulation results in both the cases prove the effectiveness of the controllers. When the load power demand is more than the PV generation, the battery should provide the extra power and when PV generation is more than the load power demand, the battery should store the extra power. This proves the power balance condition of the system. This is achieved through proper charging and discharging control of Lead-acid battery by controlling the duty cycle of the bidirectional buck-boost converter.

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